
**SUCCESSFUL SCHOOL MANAGEMENT IN INDIA: NAVODAYA
VIDYALAYA SAMITI**

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Abstract:

Education is the cornerstone of human resource development and is crucial to restoring harmony to the nation's socioeconomic structure. Each person of the country needs the nurturing and care in the form of basic education to create a higher quality of life because its population are its most significant resource. Building solid educational foundations will enable our citizens to flourish holistically. This paper is based on the work of Navodaya Vidyalaya Organization which includes the measures steps taken for the development of students, especially the deprived and underprivileged children to show its Successful School Management all over India.

Rajiv Gandhi, the former Indian prime minister, is credited with coming up with the concept of Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya, in order to provide quality along with social justice, the National Policy on Education, 1986 included the idea of establishing a JNV in each district of India. Targeting bright pupils who lack access to accelerated learning because of socioeconomic, social, and rural constraints, this system of central schools for talented students primarily from rural areas in India. The Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti, an autonomous organization falling under the Ministry of Human Resource Development's Department of Literacy and School Education, is in charge of running Navodaya Vidyalaya.

There is utmost progress to prepare their teachers according to the scenario. The new education policy with the collaboration of the Central Institute of Indian Languages Mysuru. The Navodaya Vidyalaya system is a singular experiment, unmatched in India's and other countries' histories of schooling. The collaboration of NVS with CIIL (Central Institute of Indian Languages Mysuru) to train the stakeholders for NEP2020 is discussed in the paper which shows the keen interest to contribute towards fulfilling the mission and vision of 'EK BHARAT SHRESHT BHARAT' of the country. The exchange program's mission is also the part to "enrich social content and promote national integration."

Keywords: Successful School Management in India, the stakeholders, building solid educational foundations, Exchange Program's Mission, deprived and underprivileged.

Introduction:

Residential schools, known as Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya, were envisioned to showcase the best rural talent under the National Policy on

Education of 1986. The Idea of making high-quality education accessible for all children, regardless of their ability to pay for it, so that those with unique aptitudes or talents would have the chance to

advance more quickly. Where the underprivileged group of learners would be able to go hand in hand with the privileged peers with the same standard thanks to such education. It is an Indian central school system for underprivileged areas that lack access to accelerated learning because of their socioeconomic, social, and rural limitations.

The Navodaya Vidyalaya System started a novel practice, is now unmatched history of schooling in India. Its relevance originates from the decision to focus on high achievers from remote regions and the commitment to derive them with a top-notch education is comparable to that provided by the best residential school systems. Navodaya Vidyalaya is affiliated with CBSE. It is a co-educated education institution that provides residential facilities to students from class VI to class XII. Free school clothes, boarding, accommodation, stationery, and transportation are all offered to pupils by Navodaya Vidyalaya. (Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti). The Samiti has eight regional offices, including ones in Bhopal, Chandigarh, Hyderabad, Jaipur, Lucknow, Patna, Pune, and Shillong in addition to its headquarters in NOIDA (UP). Residential schools for both sexes known as "Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya."

JNVs were created in order to identify gifted kids in rural areas of the nation and give them access to a top-notch education so they could compete without

being at a disadvantage. All of the JNVs are entirely residential, co-educational schools. A large number of children from different states apply every year for admission to these schools.

The executive committee is in charge of overseeing all operations, including the distribution of funds to the Samiti, and it has the authority to use all of the Samiti's powers. Two subcommittees, the Academic Advisory Committee, and the Finance Committee support it. As a Vikas Nidhi, there is only a little monthly price of Rs. 600. According to the following regulations set forth by Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti Headquarters, Vidyalaya Vikas Nidhi is paid. Since its creation in 1987, this clause has been a component of the NVS Education code.

This paper is largely focusing on the running of Navodaya as a hit unit of the educational system of India at the ground level for underprivileged groups of proficient and talented youngsters and giving its helping hand in improving schooling within the country.

Medium of Education:

The medium of instruction given to the students from VII or VIII Class is their mother tongue/regional language. The common medium is Hindi/English in all Navodaya Vidyalaya.

NVS has students from underprivileged groups therefore it is a must to have a

medium of instruction need to be in their mother tongue/regional language.

AIMS of the Navodaya Vidyalaya:

1	Through the migration-scheme Navodaya Vidyalaya aims to ingrain values of national integration.
2	To promote the understanding of unity in diversity and cultural heritage, efforts are taken by the Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti.
3	The Navodaya Vidyalaya program is the top secondary and senior secondary education program in the nation.
4	The importance of the programme originates from the choice to pay attention on gifted rural youngsters and the dedication to offering them with an fantastic education on par with that presented via the best residential school systems.
5	It was believed that children with special skills should be given the opportunity to grow more swiftly by making high-quality education available to them, regardless of their capacity to pay for it.

Objectives of Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti (Department of School Education and Literacy)

The following objectives will be pursued by the educational institutions that

will be created, endowed, administered, controlled, and governed (henceforth referred to as "Navodaya Vidyalaya"), as well as any acts and tasks essential for or beneficial to their development:

	To set up infrastructure for instruction using Hindi and English as a common language throughout the nation at an appropriate moment.
	Provide a single core curriculum to assure standards comparability and to help students and teachers better comprehend the shared and diverse traditions of our people.
	To gradually transfer students from one area of the nation to another in each school to encourage national integration and improve the social curriculum.
	To act as a focal point for raising the standard of teaching in schools by giving instructors hands-on experience, sharing resources, and sharing facilities.
	To create, develop, maintain, and manage hostels for Navodaya Vidyalaya students.
	To support, create, and manage more institutions as needed for the Society's objectives to be furthered in any region of India.
	To take any and all actions deemed necessary, incidental, or helpful to achieving all or any of the society's objectives.

Figure 1 Objectives of Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti (<https://navodaya.gov.in/nvs/en/Home1/>)

The Sole Vision:

“To provide good quality modern education including a strong component of culture, inculcation of values, awareness of the environment, adventure activities and physical education- to the talented children predominantly from the rural areas without regard to their family's socio-economic conditions.”

Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti was established to improve the educational system for every student in India. After

independence, the education system needed a boost to reach the world's expectations and demands. This Samiti was made to put efforts in order to develop a strong curriculum, provide better quality education and work on student's skill development.

The Samiti aimed to improve education in rural areas and students below the poverty level in urban districts. Important features of the Navodaya Vidyalaya are

Student migration toward National Integration:

The movement of students from one Navodaya Vidyalaya in one language region to another in different language region is a distinguishing aspect of the

Navodaya Vidyalaya Scheme, which aims to enhance understanding of India's cultural and linguistic diversity. According to this Plan, 30 % of Class-IX students from one JNV move to another JNV for the academic year.

Fig 2 A picture from the NVS Portal of Migration of Students for National Integration (<https://navodaya.gov.in/nvs/nvs-school/HASSAN/en/academics/Migration/>)

The Three-language Formula for migration:

For a year, linked JNVs from various linguistic regions will exchange 30% of their Class-IX pupils, which is a key component of Samiti's efforts to promote national integration. The 'Three Language Formula' will be used in accordance with this plan. Everyone must follow the formula. The Vidyalaya adheres to the standard of 3-language formula, which includes native tongue, Hindi, and English, in non-Hindi regions.

Facility for Students at Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti (Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti):

- Educational institutions with an established educational system.

- Accommodation accessories like hostel facilities and so on.
- School attire like t-shirts, sweatshirts, polo shirts, masks, etc with additional amenities like. A mess facility, science park, mathematics garden, smart room, etc.
- Textbooks for all subjects are provided to every child.
- Stationery is a prerequisite, including pens, pencils, erasers, scales, geometry boxes, notebooks, and schoolbags.
- It offers all requisites for daily life (Bathing soap, washing soap, Toothpaste, Toothbrush, Shoe polish, Hair oil, Washing and ironing of clothes, Sanitary napkins for girls)

The expenses that NVS will pay for students include the following:

Fig 3 Shows the expenditure of students bore by NVS

The CBSE Tuition Fee:

Navodaya Vidyalaya is bearing the actual CBSE fees for the students. Students in grades IX through XII pay a minimal monthly fee of Rs. 600 for Vidyalaya Vikas Nidhi. This fee is waived

Shweta Mishra & Dr. Navita Malik

for SC/ST students, girls, and kids from homes that fall below the poverty line (BPL). The VVN is paid in rupees. For kids whose parents work in government, 1500/- each student, per month.

The Entire Cost of Students' Train and/or Bus whether Transportation by IIIAC:

This is very clear by the heading that NVS provide the travel allowance which can be a bus, a train or AC III tire facility, whatever the convenience the child may commutes with will be bore by the organisation.

The Cost of Medical Care:

For the following JNVs: (a) All JNVs located in difficult or challenging places. It has been permitted to appoint part-time doctors to visit JNVs for two hours every day on all working days, for a fee of Rs. 20,000/- (Rupees twenty thousand rupees) each month.

In general, the medical costs at a rate of Rs. 36 per child each month for nine months equals Rs. 324.

Activities at Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti:

Fig 4 Activities at NVS

(<https://navodaya.gov.in/nvs/nvs-school/UNA/en/activities/Archieved-other-activities/>)

The JNV used to conduct certain competitions to promote sports among students. The goal of scouting is also to help create a better world by educating young people about values based on the "Scout Promise and Law" at Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya. Since 2005, the Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti has worked with the UNFPA (United Nations Population Fund Agency), NCERT, and MHRD to execute the Adolescence

Education Program (AEP). Adolescent pupils are given accurate knowledge on life skills education, and it promotes peer education on leadership traits, self-evaluation, gender equality, etc. The primary goal of the science congress is to offer high-quality education to students, to those from rural areas. Based on the children's abilities and potential for creativity, invention, investigation, questioning, and critical thinking,

Initiatives being taken by the NVS in education:

(VV <https://navodaya.gov.in/nvs/en/Home1/>)

1.Providing measures for safety and security
1.No to Corporal Punishment
1.Adopting strict anti-bullying and ragging policy
1.Admission through Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya Selection Test (JNVST)
1.Providing vocational training

The aforementioned details shed light on the amenities offered to Vidyalaya's students. Each student whose parents are government employees must pay a monthly fee of Rs. 1500 to Vikas Nidhi, this amount is also used to cover the expenses. The schools have doctors, and NVS takes care of the medical needs, but if it's necessary, an allowance is also provided based on how far the student is from the hospital.

All safety precautions are implemented, and ragging is treated as a crime in a rigorous setting. Teachers are well-instructed to refrain from using physical punishment because harsh measures may be used. NVS also prepares its students for the future by focusing on practical applications based on educational policies. Students who want to enroll in these Navodaya institutions must take the JNVST exam, which is administered each year for admission to grades 6, 9, and 11. To attend these NV schools, numerous deserving kids apply each year to attend the Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya, which are connected with the CBSE.

According to the public views, getting accepted into a JNV or KV is a

prestige issue for kids. The Central Board of Secondary Education is connected to both institutions (CBSE). Both institutions have strict selection procedures for their teachers, and they are transferrable across the nation.

The value of the teacher training program is also highly regarded, and both the facilities and the pay provided to them are up to par with Government of India standards. As a result, it is believed that the pupils in these institutions will perform substantially better than those in other schools. It will be fascinating to examine whether kids in these two systems differ in terms of their skills, particularly in terms of intelligence.

NEP 2020: Implementation Strategies by NVS:

Run the Program to build capacity while collaborating with other Groups in the eye of NEP2020.

Online Pedagogical Leadership Training for NVS Principals Over a Five-Day Period in Partnership with NIEPA New Delhi. NEP-2020 mandates that principals create and implement

pedagogical strategies that are based on competency-based education.

To prepare principals for master-level training in pedagogical leadership that they may offer to other principals, NVS organized a five-day online training course in collaboration with NIEPA, New Delhi, in two batches of 50 participants each.

A six-day training program for teachers of regional languages was created in collaboration with CIIL, Mysore, in light of NEP-2020. NVS language instructors for 45 Malayalam, 106 Marathi, 94 Kannada, and 69 Telugu have all received training in light of the importance of regional languages as per NEP-2020.

Role of CIIL (Central Institute of Indian Languages Mysuru):

To implement National Education Policy 2020, the NTS-I of CIIL has organized an online capacity-building language training program for the Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti (NVS) teachers of regional languages. This program aims to increase teachers' awareness of an agreement on specialized scientific topics, cutting-edge tools, approaches, and methodologies common in the area of regional language education and mother tongue education. This curriculum offered in a total of 14 languages by NVS and CIIL to improve the capability of four languages—Kannada, Marathi, Malayalam, and Telugu—ran in January and February 2021.

According to Prof. C. G. Venkatesha Murthy, Director of CIIL, CIIL is committed to the protection, maintenance, and promotion of all Indian languages regardless of their sociolinguistic status and is fully equipped to provide training. Language teachers will show to be the foundation for the successful implementation of NEP-2020, as per Vinayak Garg, Commissioner, NVS. Its focus was to make them capable of incorporating LSRW techniques into their native tongues and regional tongues for the improvement of a person's cognitive growth. These training programs will play an important role in the development and promotion of Indian languages and thereby they will also contribute towards fulfilling the 'EK BHARAT SHRESHT BHARAT' vision of the country (Prof Shailendra Mohan January 22, 2021).

A total of 350 TGTs will receive training in the most recent methods, tools, strategies, and technology for language education, assessment, and evaluation.

Conclusion:

Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti has succeeded in achieving its original goals. One Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya is to be constructed in each district in accordance with government policy. It is delivering a high-quality modern education to gifted children, primarily from rural areas, without taking into account their family's socioeconomic situation, including a significant component of cultural inculcation of values, awareness of the

environment, adventure activities, and physical education. Candidates chosen from rural areas fill at least 75% of the seats in a district. Reservations are made for SC and ST students based on their population, with a cap of the national average for these groups.

At the end of the academic year 2021–2022, there were 2,98,401 students enrolled in Navodaya Vidyalaya. The percentage of SC/ST students in Navodaya Vidyalaya is significantly higher than the national average (15% SC & 7.5% ST). As a result, JNVs serve more SC & ST students and rural students in general than the national average. It has been working successfully to fulfill the desired outcome.

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